

Factors affecting farmers' adoption decision of innovative circular farming practices and solutions in EU.

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Abstract: The agricultural and livestock sectors are facing several challenges to achieve the current EU environmental objectives. Reducing Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions and ensuring that a great share of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium coming from renewable sources are one of the major policy goals. In this context, farmers are continuously looking to adopting innovative technologies and solutions that may ensure sustainable food production systems. The adoption process of innovations at the farm level based on the circular economy concept may improve resource efficiency, allow the reuse and recovery of nutrients and reduce the negative effect of emissions on soils, water and air. The farmers' decision to accept and adopt the innovative solutions depends mainly on the initial investments and return, benefits and costs, farm structure, farmers' socio-economic characteristics, farmers' attitudes, opinions and behavior and, external markets conditions among other determinant reasons. This study aims at identifying the determinant factors and barriers that affect farmers' adoption of several Circular Agronomy Solutions using a semi-structured questionnaire on an exploratory sample of farmers in 5 EU countries. Preliminary results showed that the level of acceptance of the proposed innovations is highly related to farmers' economic motivations and objectives. The cost of the investment, the return rate, the institutional support, risk and environmental attitude play a relevant role in the adoption decision. Results of the adoption preferences may assist policy-makers in designing more specific and efficient measures and tools that may help farmers to face the current environmental challenges and social needs.

Keywords: innovation; adoption; farmers decision; circular economy
